

ISic0994

I.Sicily inscription 0994

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

crypta D.Ioannis

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]P[A]Ω
2. εύχομένην
3. σε θεὸς[ς]τε
4. φ[αν]ώσει ΔΑΝ
5. [---]ΠΟΤ[---]ΣΟΙ
6. Δ[---]
7. ἀγα[λλο]μέ
8. νη Σωφρο
9. σύνη [χρηστή]
10. χαῖρε

Apparatus

Text of IG with slight changes based on Gualtherus' and Caietanus' diplomatic transcriptions

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492621

EDCS 39102148

PHI 140472

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0174 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Boeckh, A., Franz, J., Curtius, E., Kirchhoff, A., Roehl, H. 1828-1887. Corpus Inscriptionum Graecarum. Berlin. At 3.5421

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